

Light-extinction Studies on the Reduction of Mercuric Chloride by Oxalic and Malonic Acids, Induced by Potassium Permanganate

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Neither organic acid (oxalic or malonic) nor KMnO_4 alone is able to reduce mercuric chloride, but a mixture of the two does so. This clearly suggests that as a result of interaction of the two ions (i.e. union of the acid and MnO_4^-), some active product is produced which reduces Hg^{2+} ion to Hg_2^{2+} state, as has been suggested in our previous publications¹. The time required for the production of this active product (or in other words, the time, after the mixing of the reactants, at which the precipitation of calomel just starts) has been termed as the period of induction. In the present note, light-extinction technique has been employed to investigate the period of induction of the reaction between mercuric chloride and oxalic or malonic acid in presence of KMnO_4 .

Procedure.—The experiments were made with the help of a Gallenkamp colorimeter in a reaction mixture containing 0.1*M* oxalic acid or malonic acid and 0.01*M* mercuric chloride and potassium permanganate, each, at 26°. A 6-volt bulb, operated by mains through a step-down transformer, was used as a source of light in the colorimeter. A suitable filter was employed. When the experiments were repeated at different temperatures and concentrations of the reactants, similar results were obtained. The observations are recorded in the Fig. 1.

Time in min.
[Scale: 4 div. = 1 min.]

FIG. 1. Changes in light extinction during reduction of oxalic and malonic acids, induced by KMnO_4 .

The extinction-time curves (Fig. 1) show that at first the extinction values decrease with time, reaching a minimum, and then rise again. When the reactants are mixed, formation of the complex starts¹ and the intensity of the colour of the reaction mixture falls, causing a decrease in the extinction values. But after a short period, the complex so formed begins to decompose, causing production of CO_2^- radical which instantaneously reduces Hg^{2+} ion to Hg_2^{2+} :

The reaction mixture having the precipitate so formed scatters more light than the reaction mixture before the start of the precipitation and hence, when the precipitation of the mercurous chloride starts, light-extinction values begin to rise.

1. Bansal *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 232, 235.

Rational conclusion is that the minimum of the curve provides the time when the reduction of mercuric chloride just starts.

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